

Chemistry Of Metal-Diene Complexes : ^{31}P NMR Studies of the Reaction of $(\text{COD})\text{PtCl}_2$ with Tertiary Phosphines in Methanol $^{\neq}$

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Reactions of $(\text{COD})\text{PtCl}_2$ with tertiary phosphine ligands in methanol have been studied by ^{31}P nmr spectroscopy. The formation of cationic complex $[(\text{COD})\text{PtCl}(\text{L})]^+\text{Cl}^-$, ($\text{L} = \text{Pr}^i_3\text{P}$, $\text{Ph}_2\text{Bu}^t\text{P}$, Bu_2^iMeP , Cy_3P and Bu_3^iP) as the only product in the equimolar reaction between $(\text{COD})\text{PtCl}_2$ and tertiary phosphines has been defined. In the reaction of $(\text{COD})\text{PtCl}_2$ with two mole equivalent of tertiary phosphines, formation of various intermediate complexes including $[(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{OCH}_3)\text{PtCl}]$ by the nucleophilic attack of methoxy-anion on the coordinated cyclo-octadiene has been observed.

IN transition metal catalysed organic synthesis, complex formation between a transition metal and an unsaturated organic molecule is considered to be an essential feature of the reaction. In view of this, various transition metal complexes with one or more weak donor ligands that can readily be displaced by the organic substrate, have been prepared. Cyclo-octadiene complexes of metals notably Rh and Ir have been widely utilized during recent years as catalysts towards organic substrates $^{1-5}$. Cyclo-octadiene platinum complexes such as $(\text{COD})\text{PtCl}_2$ 6 , $(\text{COD})_2\text{Pt}^7$ ($\text{COD} = \text{cyclo-octadiene}$, C_8H_{12}) have also been used frequently for the synthesis of various complexes with ligand substitution $^{8-10}$. Nucleophilic addition reactions with $(\text{COD})\text{PtCl}_2$ (1) have been studied in detail $^{11-15}$. We have recently shown 14,15 that the methoxy addition product $[(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{OCH}_3)\text{MCl}]_2$ (2) ($\text{M} = \text{Pt}$ or Pd) produces corresponding metal hydride complexes, *trans*- $\text{MH}(\text{Cl})\text{L}_2$, when reacted with tertiary phosphine ligands in methanol. In continuation of our studies on metal-diene complexes, we report here the ^{31}P nmr studies of the reactions of tertiary phosphines with $(\text{COD})\text{PtCl}_2$ (1) in methanol, which show the formation of cationic complexes $[(\text{COD})\text{Pt}(\text{Cl})\text{L}]^+\text{Cl}^-$ (3) by chloride substitution.

Experimental

Reactions were carried out under anaerobic conditions. Diethyl ether, pentane and hexane were dried and distilled over LiAlH_4 . Methanol was dried and distilled over magnesium metal. Tricyclohexyl phosphine, Cy_3P , was obtained from its carbon disulfide adduct, $\text{Cy}_3\text{P} \cdot \text{CS}_2$, by heating in ethanol under nitrogen. $\text{Ph}_2\text{P}^i\text{Cl}$, $\text{Bu}_2^i\text{P}^i\text{Cl}$ and

Pr^i_3P (Strem Chemicals) were vacuum distilled prior to use. Tri-*t*-butylphosphine was prepared from the reaction of *t*-butyl lithium, with di-*t*-butyl chlorophosphine in hexane. Similarly, di-*t*-butyl methyl phosphine was prepared from the reaction of $\text{Bu}_2^i\text{P}^i\text{Cl}$ with methyllithium. Diphenyl *t*-butylphosphine was prepared from the reaction of $\text{Ph}_2\text{P}^i\text{Cl}$ with *t*-butyllithium. $(\text{COD})\text{PtCl}_2$ was prepared from the reaction of excess 1,5-cyclooctadiene with K_2PtCl_4 in a mixture of propanol and water. A small amount of SnCl_2 was used as the catalyst in this reaction.

Proton and ^{31}P nmr spectra were recorded on Bruker-60 or 300 MHz Fourier Transform instrument. Deuterated-acetone or C_6D_6 was used as solvent with TMS as internal standard for the ^1H nmr spectra whereas ^{31}P nmr spectra were obtained in CH_3OH or C_6D_6 using H_3PO_4 as external reference. Microanalyses were performed by Atlantic Microlab, Atlanta, Georgia or M.H.W. Microanalytical Lab, Phoenix, Arizona.

Reaction of $(\text{COD})\text{PtCl}_2$ with tertiary phosphines in 1:1 molar ratio in methanol : When $(\text{COD})\text{PtCl}_2$, (1), was allowed to react with a tertiary phosphine in equimolar amount in methanol under nitrogen atmosphere and the reaction mixture was stirred magnetically at room temperature, a clear solution resulted within few min. ^{31}P NMR spectrum of this solution confirmed the reaction of phosphine with 1 forming a platinum-phosphine complex. Thus, ^{31}P nmr spectrum showed the disappearance of the starting phosphine signal and appearance of new signal associated with platinum

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satellite. Typically, when Cy_3P (0.56 gm ; 2 mmol) was added to a magnetically stirred suspension of $(COD)PtCl_2$ (0.75 gm ; 2 mmol) in methanol (≈ 50 ml) and the reaction mixture was stirred further at room temperature, a clear solution resulted within 30 min. The reaction mixture was concentrated to a small volume (≈ 10 ml) *in vacuo* and a small fraction was syringed out and used for ^{31}P nmr spectrum. The spectrum showed a singlet at $\delta 30.56$ ppm associated with platinum satellites with $J_{PtP}=2859$ Hz. No other peak due to free phosphine was observed. Dropwise addition of benzene and hexane to the remaining solution resulted in the formation of yellowish-white crystalline solid. This was filtered, washed with hexane and dried *in vacuo* (yield $\sim 70\%$). Analytical and ^{31}P nmr data are given in Table 1.

In an attempt to isolate the complex 3 ($L=Bu_3P$) from a similar reaction of $(COD)PtCl_2$ with Bu_3P , when benzene and hexane were added to the clear solution, a white solid formed which was found to be starting $(COD)PtCl_2$. Anal. Found : C, 25.9 ; H, 3.22 ; Cl, 19.2%. Calcd. for $(C_8H_{12})_2PtCl_2$: C, 25.7 ; H, 3.21 ; Cl, 19.0%. The filtrate was found to contain free tri-*t*-butyl phosphine as analyzed by 1H and ^{31}P nmr spectra.

Reaction of $(COD)PtCl_2$ with R_3P in 1:2 molar ratio in methanol : Reaction of $(COD)PtCl_2$ with two mole equivalent of a tertiary phosphine results in a clear solution in methanol at room temperature. ^{31}P NMR spectrum of this solution was found to be complex and consisted of signals due to various possible complexes (Table 2). Typically, when tricyclohexyl phosphine (0.56 gm ; 2 mmol) was added to $(COD)PtCl_2$ (0.37 gm ; 1 mmol) suspended in methanol (40 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere and

the mixture was stirred at room temperature, a clear solution resulted within 20 min. The reaction mixture was concentrated *in vacuo* and ^{31}P nmr spectrum was recorded. The spectrum showed several sets of signals explainable due to the formation of various complexes. Upon addition of benzene/hexane to this solution, an off-white crystalline solid was isolated, which corresponded in analyses to $(Cy_3P)_2PtCl_2$ (yield $\sim 65\%$). The filtrate was shown to contain 1,5-cyclooctadiene by *gc/mass spec.* Analysis of solid ; Found: C, 52.7 ; H, 8.02 ; Cl, 8.71 ; P, 7.42% Calcd. for $C_{38}H_{60}Cl_2P_2$: C, 52.3 ; H, 7.99 ; Cl 8.60 ; P, 7.51%.

Results and Discussion

When a slurry of $(COD)PtCl_2$ (1) in methanol is reacted with an equimolar amount of tertiary phosphines such as Cy_3P , Ph_2Bu^tP , Pr_3^tP , Bu_3^tP , a clear solution resulted within a few minutes. ^{31}P NMR spectrum of the solution showed only one set of signals consisting of a main peak associated with platinum satellites (Table 1), suggesting a coordination of the phosphine to the platinum. From this reaction solution crystalline solid complex has been

isolated in the cases when $L = Cy_3P$, Bu^tPh_2P and Bu_2^tMeP and corresponded in analyses to 3 (Table 1). Proton nmr spectrum of complex 3 shows two sets of signals due to olefinic protons associated with platinum satellites suggesting the presence of non-equivalent *trans* groups. In particular, a solution of 3 ($L=Bu_2^tMeP$) in d_6 -acetone shows two sets of equally intense signals at $\delta 6.20$ ppm ($J_{Pt-H}=43$ Hz) and $\delta 5.42$ ppm ($J_{Pt-H}=62$ Hz). Interestingly, the platinum phosphorus coupling constants (J_{Pt-P})

TABLE 1— ^{31}P NMR SPECTRAL DATA AND THE ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF THE PRODUCT OF THE REACTION OF $(COD)PtCl_2$ WITH TERTIARY PHOSPHINE IN 1:1 RATIO IN METHANOL

S. No.	Complex	δP (ppm)	J Pt P (Hz)	Analysis% C	Found H	Calcd. Cl
1.	$[(COD)PtCl(PPh_2Bu^t)]^+Cl^-$	33.57	3054	46.3 (46.8)	5.07 (5.03)	11.9 (11.5)
2.	$[(COD)PtCl(PPr_3^t)]^+Cl^-$	42.52	2884			
3.	$[(COD)PtCl(PBu_2^tMe)]^+Cl^-$	22.05	2895	38.4 (38.2)	6.30 (6.18)	13.7 (13.3)
4.	$[(COD)PtCl(PCy_3)]^+Cl^-$	30.56	2859	47.9 (47.7)	6.89 (6.88)	11.3 (10.9)
5.	$[(COD)PtCl(PBu_3^t)]^+Cl^-$	77.10	2932			

TABLE 2— ^{31}P NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF THE PROBABLE PRODUCTS OF THE REACTION OF $(COD)PtCl_2$ WITH TERTIARY PHOSPHINE IN 1:2 RATIO IN METHANOL

Complex 4	δP (ppm)	J_{PtP} (Hz)	Complex 5 ^a	δP (ppm)	J_{PtP}
$[(C_6H_{12}OCH_3)_2PtCl(PPr_3^t)]$	36.39	3928	$[(C_6H_{12}(OCH_3)_2)_2Pt(PPr_3^t)_2]$	28.75	1514
$[(C_6H_{12}OCH_3)_2PtCl(PBu^tPh_2)]$	39.10	4251	$[(C_6H_{12}(OCH_3)_2)_2Pt(PBu^tPh_2)_2]$	30.86	1531
$[(C_6H_{12}OCH_3)_2PtCl(PBu_3^t)]$	69.96	3843		33.47	1497
				34.58	1497

a This may not be the actual complex.

($J_{PtP}=2859-3054\text{Hz}$) (Table 1) observed for the complex 3 is found to be much smaller as compared to that of complex 4 [($C_8H_{12}OCH_3$)Pt(Cl)L], ($J_{PtP}=3843-4251\text{Hz}$), although in both complexes, the phosphine is *trans* to the olefinic carbon-carbon double bond. This implies that the Pt-P bond in complex 3 is weaker in comparison to that in 4. This is further supported by the fact that while complex 4 is quite stable in solvents like methanol, benzene, CH_2Cl_2 etc., complex 3 (when $L=Bu_3P$ or Pr_3P) dissociates back into starting complex 1 and free phosphines in solvents such as benzene or hexane.

Thus the above reaction (eq. 1) demonstrates that tertiary phosphine ligands, R_3P , have the ability to promote chloride substitution in protic solvents such as methanol, generating the corresponding cationic complexes, even in the absence of silver(I) salts. When the manuscript was under preparation, Hartley and coworkers¹⁶ reported the preparation of some cationic complexes of the type $[M(LL)(Cl)L]^+ClO_4^-$ [$M=Pt$ or Pd ; $(LL)=Ph_2PC_2H_4PPh_2$ or $Ph_2AsC_2H_4PPh_2$ and L' =tertiary phosphine] by chloride displacement using silver(I) perchlorate. However, their attempt's to displace chloride in the absence of silver(I) did not appear to succeed.

When an additional mole of the phosphine was added to the reaction (eq. 1) containing complex 3 and the reaction mixture was examined by ^{31}P nmr spectroscopy, a change in the spectrum was observed. This showed the appearance of at least three new sets of signals, none of which corresponded to free phosphine. A singlet with no platinum coupling was identified due to $(R_3PH)^+Cl^-$. A set of signals consisting of a main peak with large platinum-phosphorus coupling ($J_{PtP}\approx 4000\text{ Hz}$) (Table 2) was found to be due to complex 4 which could be prepared independently by the bridge-splitting reaction of [($C_8H_{12}OCH_3$)PtCl]₂ by appropriate phosphine¹⁵. Formation of complex 4 can be explained by the nucleophilic attack of methoxy anion on the coordinated diene⁶ in the presence of phosphine as base. As a result of this $(R_3PH)Cl$ would be formed as by-product.

Besides these signals, another set of signals is also observed. This contains two main singlets associated with platinum satellites of much smaller magnitude ($J_{PtP}\approx 1500\text{ Hz}$) (Table 2). Such small coupling constants are generally observed for phosphorus nuclei *trans* to O-bonded carbon in platinum(II) complexes¹⁷ or tetravalent platinum-phosphine complexes¹⁸. The former statement is in favour of complex 5 which is a product of nucleophilic addition of two methoxy anions. Appearance of two singlets is probably a consequence of different stereochemistry (exo and endo) of the two methoxy groups on the cyclooctadiene, causing a non-equivalent *trans* group to the phosphines. When

the methoxy-bridged dinuclear platinum complex [($C_8H_{12}OCH_3$)Pt(OCH₃)]₂ obtained from the reaction of (C_8H_{12})PtCl₂ with sodium hydroxide, was allowed to react with 4 mole equivalent of Ph_3P ,

complex 5 formed which showed a similar ^{31}P nmr spectrum. Proton nmr of this complex showed two types of methoxy signals at δ 2.88 and 3.09 ppm. Lewis and co-workers²⁰ have reported a similar reaction and have been able to isolate a complex ($C_8H_{12}acac_2$)PtL₂ (*acac*=acetylacetyl) similar to 5.

Interestingly, when the solvent of the reaction (eq. 2, $L=Cy_3P$) was removed and the residue was crystallized from CH_3OH/C_6H_6 /hexane, crystals of $(Cy_3P)_2PtCl_2$ were obtained in $\sim 70\%$ yield, and free cyclooctadiene was isolated (by glc) from the organic phase. It is important to mention here that no insoluble solid was precipitated from methanol solution of this reaction even after keeping for over 2 weeks, suggesting the absence of any pre-formed $(Cy_3P)_2PtCl_2$ (7) before crystallization. Formation of complex (7) in the reaction might suggest a possibility of complex 6 in solution. However, such a complex should show a large platinum-phosphorus coupling constants ($J_{Pt-P}\approx 3,000-4000\text{ Hz}$) in the ^{31}P nmr spectrum. Since no such signals have been observed, the possibility of the existence of complex 6 in solution can be ruled out. Probably during the crystallization, attack of chloride ions on the complex 5 takes place to give the $(Cy_3P)_2PtCl_2$ complex²⁰. Although, at present, we do not have any other evidence in favor of the above possible intermediate (5), efforts are being made to solve this problem.

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